

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Hydric stress condition and soil erosion maps

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

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Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organise their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated with the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organised by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Executive Summary

The deliverable here reported includes an estimation of the annual mean soil loss determined with the soil erosion maps across the Ardivestra, Versa, and Tidone Pavese watersheds determined with the updated Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model. By leveraging the same dataset used for the RUSLE model, a 2D hydrologic/hydraulic model was calibrated to precisely identify areas susceptible to soil erosion under current conditions. This model harnesses hydrodynamic insights, such as water depth and velocity, obtained through the analysis of rainfall-runoff scenarios with short-return periods. The preliminary results obtained aim to deliver scientifically grounded assessments of erosion-prone areas in the Oltrepò, ultimately reducing management costs.

A) Soil erosion maps

The maps related to the areas subject to erosion in the four watersheds of the Oltrepò Pavese (Ardivestra, Versa, Scuropasso, Tidone Pavese) were generated following the RUSLE (Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation) methodology, the latest update of which is in 2022.

The evaluation of the annual mean soil loss A , according to the RUSLE method, depends on the following factors:

$$A = R \times K \times LS \times C \times P$$

A = soil loss (ton/ha/yr)

R = rainfall erosivity

K = soil erodibility

LS = length and steepness of the slope

C = land cover

P = agricultural practices management factor (value equal to 1)

Figure 1: Annual mean soil loss in the Ardivestra, Scuropasso, Versa and Tidone Pavese watersheds.

The annual mean soil loss was calculated to be approximately 0.83, 1.29, 1.09, and 0.82 in Ardivestra, Scuropasso, Versa, and Tidone Pavese, respectively.

The different intervals depicted on the map represent distinct levels of soil loss severity. The area of each watershed interested in each annual mean soil loss interval is reported in table 1.

Annual mean soil loss [t/ha/yr]	Area affected by soil erosion [km ²]			
	Ardivestra	Versa	Scuropasso	Tidone Pavese
<1	34.92	34.92	23.12	34.91
1-3	8.88	15.70	12.36	5.04
3-6	2.33	3.53	3.81	2.41
6-11	0.57	0.65	0.80	0.72
11-22	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.20
22-33	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.03
>33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01

Table 1: Area of the watershed interested in each annual mean soil loss interval.

In the following chapters, the methodology applied for the creation of the soil loss map in Figure 1 is described.

R Factor – Rainfall erosivity factor

A multidimensional map was generated using data from the ARCIS precipitation climate database (Climatological Archive for Central-Northern Italy), based on a collection of daily rainfall data throughout the entire territory of central and Northern Italy and referring to a regular cell size of 5.5 km. The period considered was from 1 January 2001 to 31 December 2021. Once the multidimensional map was obtained, the following formula was applied for the annual estimate of R factor (Bertolini et. al. 2004).

$$R = \left(\sum_{1}^n \sum_{1}^{365} (0.11 * P_{day}^{1.82}) \right) / n$$

Where 0.11 is a constant, n is equal to the number of years considered, and P_{day} is the average daily rainfall data.

Figure 2: R Factor map for Northern Italy

K Factor – Soil erodibility factor

The susceptibility of soils to erosion depends on several characteristics of the soil which, according to the original methodology (Wischmeier et al. 1971), are effectively represented by 4 main factors: texture (sandy and silty fraction), organic substance, structure, permeability.

In the original nomogram, these quantities are related, classified if necessary, according to the indications of the Soil Survey Manual (USDA 1951). The following derived algorithm allows faster calculations of K , at least for cases where silt does not exceed 70 %:

$$K = \frac{(2.77 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot (12 - OM) \cdot M^{1.14} + 4.28 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (s - 2) + 3.29 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (p - 3))}{100}$$

where:

- OM is the percentage of organic matter;
- M is the product of the percentage of fine silt plus very fine sand times the percentage of total sand plus total silt:

$$M = \% (\text{fraction } 0.002 - 0.1 \text{ mm}) * \% (\text{fraction } 2 - 0.002 \text{ mm})$$

- s is the shape of the soil structural aggregates (1 = very fine granular; 2 = fine granular; 3 = medium and coarse granular, 4 = prismatic, lamellar and massive);
- p is the permeability class (1 = rapid > 0.212 cm/min; 2 = moderate to rapid 0.1 – 0.21 cm/min; 3 = moderate 0.003 – 0.1 cm/min; 4 = slow to moderate 0.008 – 0.03 cm/min; 5 = slow 0.0016 – 0.008 cm/min; 6 = very slow < 0.0016 cm/min).

Given the relatively constant characteristics of soil structure and texture over time, the final raster of the factor was used.

Figure 3: K Factor map in the Ardivestra, Scuropasso, Versa and Tidone Pavese watersheds.

LS Factor – Slope -length factor

Slope-length factor (L) and slope steepness factor (S) are topographical factors that indicate the effect of topography on erosion horizontally. The distance from the point of origin of overland flow to the point where deposition begins due to a decrease in slope gradient is known as slope length. Slope steepness also influences soil erosion and is signified by slope gradients. This factor is attributed to higher overland flow velocities and correspondingly higher erosion.

The L and S were calculated starting from the Lombardy DEM with cells of 20x20 m. The L factor is defined as the ratio between the soil loss of a parcel of land that has any free length (the length to be used for the local/regional scale to be defined) and the reference (length) equal to 22.13 m.

The S factor, on the other hand, expresses the ratio between the soil loss of a plot of land inclined by S and that of the reference plot (with S) equal to 9%. The calculation of the LS factor is finally based on the following formula:

$$LS = \left(FlowAccumulation * \frac{CellSize}{22.13} \right)^m * \left(\left(\frac{Sen(slope*0.01745)}{0.09} \right) \right)^m * (1 + m)$$

where m and n are constant parameters, calibrated based on the availability of information on runoff characteristics and soil conditions.

The m parameter can vary between 0.4 and 0.6 (here a uniform value of 0.4 was used). The n parameter ranges from 1.0 to 1.4 (here a uniform value of 1.4 was used). The *FlowAccumulation* is a raster that represents the weight of the accumulation of each cell as the accumulation weight for all cells that lie below that slope direction. This raster is produced starting from the Digital Terrain Model (DTM) which describes the morphology of the region. The *CellSize* is the size of the DTM raster which, in the present case, is 20x20m. Instead, 22.13 m is the length of the reference plot of the RUSLE model. The Slope represents the inclination of the cells in radians. The maximum inclination of the reference plot for the RUSLE model is 0.09 %.

Figure 4: LS Factor map in the Ardivestra, Scuropasso, Versa and Tidone Pavese watersheds.

C Factor – Land use factor

The dimensionless C factor calculates how the ratio between the loss of soil in different cultivation and coverage conditions of the areas considered and the loss relating to the standard plot (bare fallow) in the same climatic, pedological and morphological conditions is distributed over the course of the year. The C factor summarises the result of the action of many different factors on soil loss, factors that the original methodology evaluates separately in detail: vegetation cover, roots, organic residues incorporated into the soil, soil management. It is, therefore, a numerical factor that varies from 0 to 1, with the lowest values significantly reducing the loss of soil expressed, traditionally, in t/ha per year. Higher values, closer to 1, instead represent those land use situations that offer poor protection and, therefore, a modest or null reduction in soil loss.

The C factor was applied to the land use cover of the Lombardy Region- DUSAF 7, 2023. The values of the C factor were determined by taking as reference the values defined by REA based on the DUSAF 6, 2018 classifications, in which the land use categories are very similar.

Figure 5: C Factor map in the Ardivestra, Scuropasso, Versa and Tidone Pavese watersheds.

B) Hydrologic/hydraulic model

Topographic analysis and design of a triangular mesh

The hydrologic/hydraulic model was generated by using as input the same Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) employed for the RUSLE model. The DEMs were imported in the Surface-water Modelling System (SMS) software for the optimization of the computational grid (triangular mesh) for Ardivestra, Versa, Scuropasso and Tidone Pavese. The refined grids have a uniform triangular mesh resolution with a cell size of 3 m. Thus, the computational domains have 1.131.948, 1.371.662, 1.038.897 and 1.020.232 elements for Ardivestra, Versa, Scuropasso and Tidone Pavese, respectively.

Figure 6: Example of triangular mesh.

Hydrologic and hydraulic variables

A synthetic storm event was generated considering a return period of 2 years. The rainfall intensity-duration curve was taken from the Regional Agency for the Protection of the Environment (ARPA) website, considering data from 1987 to 2021. The temporal distribution of the rainfall event was evaluated using the Chicago hyetograph. Net rains were estimated using the original Soil Conservation Service (now named Natural Resources Conservation Service – NRCS) Curve Number (SCS-CN) method (SCS 1985). This approach is based on a single parameter (CN) per each watershed. As for the CN II estimation, a uniform value was assumed in the watersheds. Then, the spatial weighted average value, based on the area covered by each class, was computed to provide an estimation of the net rainfall. The CN II values were found to be equal to 84, 88, and 89 for the Ardivestra, Versa, and Scuropasso basins, respectively. Considering the scenario-based approach used in this work, AMC (Antecedent Moisture Conditions) levels were arbitrarily assumed in such a way as to cover a wide range of cases. Therefore, CN III and the CN I values were also computed. Hence, the synthetic gross rainfall

event related to the return time was manipulated using the SCS-CN approach. The hydrologic/hydraulic model was initiated using the generated synthetic net rainfalls. The model provided reliable results in runoff simulations at the watershed scale. As the model required the estimation of the Manning roughness coefficients, a non-uniform distribution of the roughness coefficients was assumed. The Manning coefficients were derived according to Chow (1959) based on the homogeneous land use map, as usually performed in 1D and 2D computations. The spatial weighted Manning values used were 0.05, 0.055, and 0.055 for Ardivestra, Versa, and Scuropasso (Tidone Pavese is still under evaluation). Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the map of the preliminary results obtained on the maximum flooded areas and the map of flow velocity computed using the grid for the rainfall hyetograph. The maps are still under revision, and thus, they are not in the final version yet. The highest value of water depth was obtained for the Versa watershed (4.3 m), followed by Scuropasso (2.6 m) and Ardivestra (2.5 m).

Figure 7: Map of the maximum flooded areas in the Ardivestra, Scuropasso and Versa watersheds.

Figure 8: Flow velocity of the Ardivestra watershed.

Bed shear stress

Bed shear stress is a fundamental variable that links flow conditions to sediment transport. It is, however, difficult to estimate this variable accurately, particularly in complex flow fields.

Shear stress is an important parameter in hydraulics and river engineering which provides an index of fluid force per unit area on the surface of the watershed (stream bed and hillslope) and is related to sediment transport and deposition in many theoretical and empirical approaches of sediment transport. The rate of sediment transport in a channel depends on the shear stress τ_0 which was computed by considering the water depth and the flow velocity derived from the hydrologic/hydraulic model.

$$\tau_0 = \gamma * \frac{n^2 * u^2}{h^{1/3}}$$

Where γ is the density of water, n is the Manning's coefficient, u is the flow velocity, and h is the water depth.

Figure 9: Map of bed shear stress of Ardivestra watershed.

In our pursuit to estimate soil erosion areas, our investigation delved into various methodologies post the computation of bed shear stress. Among the methodologies that are still currently in exploration, a prominent avenue emerged in determining the dimensionless values of the Shield stress. This approach presents a promising trajectory in comprehending the dynamics of soil erosion, offering a nuanced understanding of the interplay between fluid flow and sediment movement. By quantifying Shield stress in dimensionless terms, we aim to establish a robust framework for predicting erosion-prone regions. This avenue showcases the potential for enriching our erosion modeling strategies and refining our predictive capabilities. The dimensionless values of the Shield stress were determined by the following equation:

$$\tau_* = \frac{\tau_0}{(\gamma_s - \gamma) * g * d_{50}}$$

Where γ_s is the density of sediment (assumed to be $2.65 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and d_{50} is the reported median grain size of the surface bed material. The surface soil-texture data was sourced from the pedologic map accessible via the Geoportal of the Lombardy Region. Utilizing this data, we determined the d_{50} parameter, employing the Wentworth scale (Wentworth, 1992). Figure 10 illustrates the median grain size of the surface bed material map. Furthermore, Figure 11 presents the outcomes of the Shield stress analysis.

Figure 10: Map of the mean grain size.

Figure 11: Dimensionless Shield stress of Ardivestra watershed

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